

STRESS CORROSION OF SHEET MOULDING COMPOUNDS

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ABSTRACT

The stress corrosion of Sheet Moulding Compounds, SMC, in acidic environments has been studied. Preliminary results show that failures are similar to stress corrosion in conventional GRP in character although there are indications that the presence of filler is modifying the fracture mechanisms. Crack growth rate experiments are found to be suitable for the study of stress corrosion in SMC, although the interpretation of results is not always straightforward.

INTRODUCTION

It is well established that certain composite materials can provide outstanding environmental resistance in aggressive environments. Typically glass fibre and carbon fibre reinforced plastics may be formulated to resist the various substances encountered in, for instance, the chemical process or water treatment industries by careful selection of matrices and the provision of adequate barrier surface layers [1]. In some instances the situation is complicated by the possibility of stress corrosion with glass fibre composites (GRP) in acidic solutions providing a good example [2]. Traditionally GRP has been used in an anti-corrosion role for components such as pipes or vessels, usually in relatively low volumes, where the material properties and laminate quality represent the best obtainable with this class of composite. GRP has not been seen as a candidate for large volume production of components for use in anti-corrosion applications where the competitive materials may be exotic metal alloys. This is largely because those forms of GRP suitable for large volume manufacture e.g. DMC and SMC are regarded as possessing inferior environmental resistance compared to carefully produced, contact moulded GRP.

The objective of this work was to assess the possibilities for developing SMC systems that offered improved corrosion resistance, particularly in aggressive environments where stress corrosion is a problem. The initial phase of the work involved characterizing the basic behaviour of conventional SMC systems under load in acid, with a view to subsequently modifying the SMC formulations in order to produce an improved, competitive material. This initial phase incorporated a study of failure mechanisms using fracture surface analysis and a verification of testing procedures that would be used to assess the relative performance of subsequent, improved formulations. Stress corrosion in unidirectional GRP produces sharp, well defined cracks and the phenomenon is suitable for study and quantification by employing fracture mechanics type experiments and monitoring crack growth rates as a function of applied stress intensity [3]. Similar techniques have been employed for the study of stress corrosion in random-in-plane glass fibre composites based on chopped strand mat, CSM, [4] but it was not clear that such an approach would be suitable for SMC where a more indistinct crack was anticipated.

MATERIALS

Two different SMC formulations were used for these initial studies. The first system, designated SMC-25, was Freeman chemical's formulation, which contained 25% by weight of random-in-plane glass fibres, calcium carbonate filler, MgO thickener and a hybrid resin formulation developed specifically to provide corrosion resistance (though not necessarily stress corrosion resistance). The other constituents usually found in SMC's such as stearates, low profile additives were also present in minor quantities. The second SMC, designated SMC-30, contained 30% by weight of fibres, was based on a conventional polyester resin system but otherwise was similar to SMC-25. Material was obtained ready processed in sheet form of a nominal thickness of 5 mm for SMC-25 and 6 mm for SMC-30.

TEST METHODS

In this programme two different loading configurations and specimen geometries were used to obtain crack growth rate data. A tapered double cantilever beam, TDCB, specimen loaded in tension as shown in figure 1 was used to measure crack growth at high values of applied stress intensity, while a notched beam loaded in four point bend, FPB, was used to obtain data on crack growth at low values of applied stress intensity. In both cases, compliance calibrations were performed which showed that the change in compliance with increasing crack length was effectively a constant. This in itself indicates that the crack tip stress intensity is constant throughout the test, independent of crack length.

The test specimens for the TDCB tests were machined from sheet material to the shape and dimensions shown in figure 1. A groove was machined along the side of the plates to ensure that crack growth was well behaved and consistent from specimen to specimen. The FPB specimens were rectangular beams cut from the sheets with a length of 190mm and width of 10mm, and thickness dependent on the thickness of the sheet. A starter crack was introduced into the beam by cutting a V-notch with a 0.5mm cutter (NB. the starter notches in both test specimen types were sharpened with a scalpel blade prior to testing). The inner span for the four point bend test was set at 50mm and the outer span at 150 mm and the tests were performed under conditions of constant applied load.

In both tests the specimens were completely immersed in the test environment which was standardized as 1M HCl, at $16^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. The growth rate of cracks in the TDCB tests was measured directly using a traveling microscope. This did not prove feasible in the FPB tests and crack growth was measured indirectly by monitoring the changes in compliance of the beam during the test.

Fig. 1 Specimen geometry and loading configuration in TDCB test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The two fracture mechanics test methods resulted in a progressive increase in crack length with time, with the rate of crack growth dependent on the magnitude of the applied stress intensity. In the case of the four point bend test, where it might be assumed that the tensile stresses acting on the material decay rapidly away from the crack tip, the crack tip remains well defined during the cracking process. Under these conditions, the crack growth rates, as indicated by the measured deflection of the beam with time, were reasonably constant, figure 2.

Crack growth in the TDCB tests exhibited some important differences. An area of damage was established at the crack tip, which consisted, not of debonding or delaminations, but of small independent (isolated) microcracks. Crack growth at the beginning of any test usually involved a period where these nuclei formed and subsequently coalesced, during which time a notional crack growth rate could be measured but which was erratic and slow. After a period of time the small cracks formed a single large crack that grew at a much faster rate until total failure of the specimen, figure 3. Examination of the crack length with time curves in figure 3 would suggest that for each specimen two characteristic growth rates exist, one at the beginning and one at the end of the test. It is postulated that during the initial stages of crack growth, when despite sharpening with a scalpel, a very sharp crack is not possible at the crack tip, then cracks may nucleate slowly ahead of the crack tip. The geometry of this test suggests that the tensile stresses acting on the material do not decay rapidly away from the crack tip as for the FPB tests which would encourage this trend. The slower crack growth rate would therefore be an artifact of the test and the faster rate one representative of the material once the crack had established itself.

Fig. 2 Variation of deflection in bending with time for different values of K_I measured in FPB tests.

Figure 4 shows the measured crack growth rates as a function of the applied stress intensity for both FPB tests and TDCB (faster rates) tests on both SMC-25 and SMC-30. Results obtained at stress intensities $> 6.31 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ ($\log K_I = 0.8$) were obtained from the TDCB tests while those $< 6.31 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ were obtained from FPB tests. The data for each SMC material would appear to belong to one set irrespective of the test method used. Furthermore the differences between the two SMC formulations is minimal.

The nature of the stress corrosion cracks themselves is very similar to those found after stress corrosion in conventional GRP [5] which exhibit a characteristically flat surface devoid of fibre or bundle pullout. Figure 5 compares the fracture surfaces of SMC-30 after rupture in air and stress corrosion in acid. Failure in air results in fibre bundles being clearly visible on the fracture surface. In acid such bundles cannot be seen and the general matrix appears pitted at low magnification. At higher magnification the pitting is shown to be the result of filler dissolution in the acid. The fracture surfaces of the fibres themselves are featureless indicating low stress fracture [6].

The results shown in figure 4 include some previously unpublished data [4] obtained by Hull and co-workers by testing CSM-polyester resin laminates using a TDCB test identical to that employed in this work. It can be seen that the simple GRP system without filler particles exhibits a different slope for the crack growth rate versus stress intensity results compared to the SMC's. The rate of crack growth is comparatively insensitive to applied stress intensity in the case of SMC which shows superior properties at high stress intensities but inferior properties at low stress intensities to CSM. This may be explained by the role of the filler in providing an easy path through the matrix for the acid by debonding or dissolving, which allows the acid to attack the fibres. In the case of the CSM laminate either a diffusion process or matrix cracking must occur before the fibres can be attacked. It is likely that in the case of SMC the failure process will be critically dependent on the nature of the filler with the resin playing only a minor role. This is in contrast to the situation found in unfilled GRP systems where the mechanical properties of the matrix can significantly influence the rate of crack growth in acid by energy dissipation at the crack tip [7].

Fig. 3 Variation of crack length with time for different values of K_I measured during TDCB tests.

Fig. 4 Comparison of crack growth rate between SMC and CSM [4].

Fig. 5 Scanning electron micrographs showing:
a) (at top) fracture surface of SMC in air;
b) (at middle) in acid;
c) (at bottom) in acid at high magnification

The superior resistance to stress corrosion crack growth offered by SMC at high levels of applied stress intensity might similarly be explained by the role of the filler which would contribute to blunting at the crack tip by debonding and dissolution processes. The exact role of the filler in controlling the fracture mechanisms will be explored in more detail in subsequent work where alternative fillers and alternative concentrations of fillers will be examined.

CONCLUSIONS

At this time only limited conclusions may be drawn regarding the mechanisms of stress corrosion crack growth in SMC. It is clear that the general characteristics are similar to stress corrosion in conventional GRP, leading to flat fracture with fibre pullout suppressed and fibre fracture occurring at low stress. It appears that the presence of filler has a significant effect on the rate of crack growth but as yet this cannot be properly explained. Certainly, fracture mechanics type crack growth experiments are suitable for characterizing and quantifying stress corrosion in SMC, although the interpretation of the results needs to be handled carefully, particularly when the double cantilever beam configuration is used.

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